

Archaeological Market Survey 2016-17

Prepared for the Chartered Institute for Archaeologists and the Federation of Archaeological Managers and Employers

Archaeological Market Survey 2017

This report has been prepared by Landward Research Ltd in its professional capacity as research, training and project management specialists, with reasonable skill, care and diligence within the agreed scope and terms of contract and taking account of the manpower and resources devoted to it by agreement with its clients, and is provided by Landward Research Ltd solely for its clients, the Chartered Institute for Archaeologists and the Federation of Archaeological Managers and Employers. It may be further distributed as the clients see fit if Landward Research Ltd is fully credited as the originator of this report and Kenneth Aitchison is fully credited as the author.

Author

Kenneth Aitchison

Publication Date

October 2017

This publication is © Landward Research Ltd and is released under a CC BY-SA 4.0 licence.

[Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/)

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project was commissioned by the Chartered Institute for Archaeologists and the Federation of Archaeological Managers and Employers and funded by the Chartered Institute for Archaeologists, the Federation of Archaeological Managers and Employers and Historic England.

Kate Geary, Nick Shepherd and Tim Malim acted as the Project Board.

So Young Ann undertook the data analysis.

Thanks to all the respondents who provided the data. Your time and knowledge have been the building blocks of this study.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This *Archaeological Market Survey* report is on the State of the Market for Archaeological Services in the United Kingdom in 2016-17. It has been prepared by Landward Research Ltd on behalf of the Chartered Institute for Archaeologists (CifA), FAME (Federation of Archaeological Managers and Employers) and Historic England.

The survey has gathered data via a questionnaire sent to FAME members and CifA Registered Organisations, therefore the focus is primarily on the commercial archaeology sector. In addition, some limited subsidiary data have been examined for the numbers of archaeologists employed by planning authorities, as this is also pertinent to understanding the state of the archaeological market.

The overall aims of this survey are to provide:

- a unique analysis of the archaeological sector as part of the overall UK economy;
- statistics that allow estimation of total value of the sector to the economy;
- data on indicative numbers of employed professional archaeologists;
- data for analysis of long-term sustainability for the sector;
- an indication of social benefit through outreach;
- data that can enable informed lobbying to help protect the UK's heritage; and
- to support planning effectively for the future so that the profession is sustainable and results in a benefit for society

In financial year 2016-17 commercial archaeology grew in terms of the number of employees working in the sector, but levels of financial turnover decreased and profit levels were unchanged.

The sector was not as confident as it had been a year earlier.

The majority of businesses in the sector did not expect to expand significantly in the next year (2017-18) (e.g. in premises, vehicles, capital equipment), but they had increased their staff complements (and continued to plan to do further in the next year). While staffing levels were increasing, average levels of turnover (and so turnover per staff member) were falling slightly.

This meant that productivity levels were low and falling. Lack of capital investment at a time of staffing increase has been recognised as a component of weak productivity growth across the construction sector¹, to which applied archaeological practice clearly belongs. This is interpreted as representing cautiousness when times are still uncertain, as adding to payroll is a more flexible expense than investing in capital-heavy equipment or premises, the costs of which are more difficult to reduce in downturns.

No figures are available for the sector's investment in research and development.

The sector continues to have limited confidence in planning policy frameworks, and does not consider that local planning authorities are being provided with sufficient professional advice.

¹ The Economist vol 424, number 9054 August 19th-25th 2017 "Construction: how to build better", p. 10; "The construction industry: least improved", pp 55-56.

Employment

- An estimated 4,351 people were working in UK applied, commercial archaeology in 2016-17. This was more than immediately before the economic downturn of 2007-08.
- It is estimated that the applied, commercial archaeological workforce grew by 13.2% in financial year 2016-17.
- In comparison with the previous year, the rate of workforce expansion had increased; the applied, commercial archaeological workforce had expanded by 9.9% in 2015-16.
- In 2016-17, the number of archaeological staff providing expert advice to local planning authorities decreased by 3.3% (a loss of 8.9 FTE posts).
- Together, these changes combine to result in the net number of people working in professional archaeology in the UK growing by 8.7% in financial year 2016-17 to an estimated total of 6,253 individuals. This figure combines the numbers working in applied, commercial archaeology, curatorial archaeology (archaeologists advising local planning authorities) and all other areas of archaeological employment..
- The ongoing increase in jobs with permanent contracts that started in 2014-15 has not been simply a response to an increase in short-term fieldwork, as that would likely be represented by a disproportionate increase in the percentage of fixed-term posts.

Financial Performance

- The average (mean) reported UK turnover for an applied archaeology company in 2016-17 was £2.3m, a decrease of 20% over the year since March 2016. 2015-16 may have been an abnormal year – overall revenue and profitability increased dramatically in that year, and then fell back in 2016-17 (although the medium-term trend is towards growth in revenue and profits).
- In 2016-17, 1% of the turnover of UK applied archaeology companies was generated from non-UK work.
- It is estimated that the total revenue of UK commercial archaeology in 2016-17 was approximately £228m.
- Profit (or 'surplus') levels remained low – an average of 5.2%, the same level as reported in 2015-16.
- Salaries typically rose in line with inflation in 2016-17 (CPI at the census date was 2.3%).
- Charge-out rates rose by 3.1% on average. As more staff had been recruited, this may either indicate a rise in value or that lower paid staff are forming a larger part of the workforce.
- Average turnover per member of staff in 2016-17 was £45,309, a slight decrease from 2015-16 of 0.7%
- Many of the largest employers are constituted as not-for-profit organisations.
- Overall, the financial performance statistics suggest that the sector may be approaching maximum capacity – it did not grow in terms of turnover in 2016-17, despite staff complements increasing (meaning productivity was falling), and profit levels had stabilised.

Market Sectors

- The overwhelming majority of income came from private sector clients (81%, a slight increase from 79% in 2015-16).
- The most important market sector continued to be residential development, which provided 42% of income (a decline from 53% in 2015-16), followed by commercial and industrial development. The catchall “any other services not categorised above” category provided 8.8% of sectoral income, and increase from 0.3% in 2015-16.

Business Confidence

- While the sector in 2017 was still relatively confident, levels of confidence in future market conditions had declined since 2016.
- The majority of respondents in 2017 expected to maintain or increase staffing levels in 2017-18, although the sector overall was not as confident of doing this as it had been in 2016.
- While there was overall confidence that market conditions would not deteriorate in 2017-18, the sector was not as confident about the future as it had been one year before (which in turn was not as confident as the sector had been in 2015).
- Most respondents expected there would be no business failures in the sector in the next year.
- Respondents generally did not expect to expand their businesses in 2017-18. This was the first time since 2013 that expansion was not anticipated by the majority of respondents. This is surprising given anticipated expansion of workloads and concerns that were raised over recruitment.

Skills, Training and Qualifications

- For the first time since this survey series began in 2008, fieldwork skills were not the area where skills loss was most frequently identified; desk-based or environmental assessment was the area where most respondents identified that they had lost skills.
- As in 2016 and 2015, more respondents reported buying-in skills than reported losing them, with fieldwork skill and artefact / ecofact conservation being the areas where skills were most often bought in from subcontractors.
- It has now become the norm for the areas where training was focussed to match reasonably closely to the areas where skills were being reported as being lost - so these skills gaps (skills that existing staff needed but lacked) were being tackled by investment in training. This has been the case since 2014.
- Employers continue to be supportive of the NVQ in Archaeological Practice, and many would be interested in supporting an Apprentice in Historic Environment Practice.

Forms of Contract

- Respondents typically use an exchange of letters/emails without detailed contracts. However a range of Forms of Contract were identified as being used; ICE standard Forms are not used as often as either contractors' or clients' own standard terms and conditions.

Perceptions

- Respondents were unsure whether the economic climate for development would improve in the next year (2017-18), and were less confident of improvement than they had been a year previously.
- Respondents were unsure whether their heritage teams would grow, but were more confident that their teams would not get smaller.
- Late payment of bills and non-payment were both considered to be slightly more problematic than they had been in 2015-16.
- Respondents continued to be unsure about the assertions that either “current national planning policy frameworks are making it easier to justify heritage work and revenue levels” or that “current national planning policy frameworks weaken the case for heritage work and revenue levels”. Sentiment in both cases had become slightly more positive than in 2016.
- They continued to agree that a shortage of heritage staff in local planning authorities was a major constraint on heritage projects (which could affect income generation).

Response Rate

- Response levels were good. There was a slight decline in the percentage of organisations providing data (55.7% declining from 56.4% in 2016).

Future Work

- This study will be repeated to gather data for 2017-18 when it is intended that this will form part of the quinquennial Profiling the Profession project which gathers comparable data from the entire archaeological profession in the UK.

Contents

ARCHAEOLOGICAL MARKET SURVEY 2016-17	1
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	3
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1 INTRODUCTION	10
1.1 Responses	11
1.2 FAME Membership	12
1.3 CIfa Registered Organisations	12
1.4 Constitution	12
1.5 Location of Head and Subsidiary Offices	14
1.6 Years Trading	17
2 STAFF NUMBERS	18
2.1 Employment	19
2.1.1 Total Staff	19
2.1.2 Staff Nationalities	20
2.1.3 Total Fee Earners	20
2.1.4 Overseas Staff	20
2.1.5 Total Employment in UK Archaeology	21
2.2 Contracts	23
2.3 Staff Turnover	24
2.4 Staff Lost From the Sector	25
2.5 Salaries	26
2.6 Charge-out Rates	27
3 FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE	28
3.1 Turnover	28
3.2 Profit Levels	31
3.3 Funding Sources (areas of activity as turnover)	32
3.4 Market Sectors	33
4 FORMS OF CONTRACT	36
5 BUSINESS CONFIDENCE	37
5.1 Staffing Levels	38
5.2 Market Conditions	39
5.3 Businesses Ceasing Trading	40

5.4	Expansion	42
6	SKILLS, TRAINING AND QUALIFICATIONS.....	44
6.1	Areas of Skills Losses.....	44
6.2	Areas of Skills Buy-in.....	45
6.3	Areas of Training	46
6.4	Skills Issues Across the Sector	47
6.5	NVQ.....	48
6.6	Apprenticeship	48
7	PERCEPTIONS.....	49
8	FURTHER COMMENTS.....	51
	APPENDIX – QUESTIONNAIRE	52

1 INTRODUCTION

Economic changes that began in the autumn of 2008 have impacted significantly upon archaeological practice in the UK.

The Chartered Institute for Archaeologists (CIfA) and the Federation of Archaeological Managers and Employers (FAME) have collected data on employment and skills issues in applied archaeological practice since October 2008. A series of nine quarterly surveys were initially conducted, gathering and presenting data from October 2008 to April 2011, and subsequently, CIfA and FAME commissioned Landward Research Ltd to gather data on a six-monthly basis and to present reports on the state of the archaeological market. The December 2012 report² was combined with the sector wide *Archaeology Labour Market Intelligence: Profiling the Profession 2012-13*³ report.

The effects of the economic situation began to directly impact upon commercial, applied archaeology from 2008 onwards. In 2010 and 2011, the changing economic effects began to be felt in the fields of archaeological services to local authorities, in national heritage agencies and in universities. The full effects of these changes on employment patterns within archaeology were not made clear until results of the pan-sectoral *Archaeology Labour Market Intelligence: Profiling the Profession 2012-13* project revealed the profundity of change with a considerable depth of job losses across the whole sector.

The reports on those earliest surveys are available on the CIfA website via the [Recession – managing and planning](#) page and on the FAME website <http://www.famearchaeology.co.uk/>.

The Chartered Institute for Archaeologists continues to need up-to-date research to be best able to support their membership by informing the Institute and its members about the effects of the economic situation on archaeology. The Federation of Archaeological Managers and Employers also seeks to provide market intelligence to its members to help them compete effectively. The fact that both organisations have commissioned this survey demonstrates the value of the information for advocacy of archaeology at Westminster and national parliaments.

Together with Historic England, CIfA and FAME have commissioned Landward Research Ltd to continue to analyse and evaluate the state of the market for archaeological services, examining employment, turnover, market segmentation and other relevant topics.

This exercise is being carried out on an annual basis over five years, collecting data for the entire UK for every year from 2013-14 up to and including 2017-18, when it is intended that the *Profiling the Profession* series of projects will continue their quinquennial cycle. It will also ensure that the data gathered will be able to contribute directly to an intended future *Profiling the Profession 2017-18* project, thus ensuring that the funders will have a full role in guiding the design and then delivery of that project. The report presented here is primarily

² Aitchison, K. 2013. *State of the Archaeological Market December 2012*. Landward Research Ltd.
<http://www.landward.eu/State%20of%20the%20Archaeological%20Market%20-%20December%202012%20050913.pdf>

³ Aitchison, K. & Rocks-Macqueen, D. 2013. *Archaeology Labour Market Intelligence: Profiling the Profession 2012-13*. Landward Research Ltd.
<http://www.landward.eu/Archaeology%20Labour%20Market%20Intelligence%20Profiling%20the%20Profession%202012-13.pdf>

based on data gathered from FAME member organisations and CifA Registered Organisations, who are considered to represent the majority of employers working in commercial, client-funded applied archaeology.

The data gathered applied on the 31st March 2017, and so this report is on the situation at the end of financial year 2016-17. The survey was issued shortly before the UK General Election on 8th June 2017 with the survey closing after the result of that election was known.

Throughout, comparisons are made with the results of the *Archaeological Market Survey 2016⁴* and *Archaeological Market Survey 2015⁵* projects, both of which gathered data from the same survey population as the current report (FAME members and CifA Registered Organisations).

Data have also been incorporated from the Historic England / ALGAO / IHBC report on local authority staff resources⁶ regarding archaeological staff advising local planning authorities in England.

Two changes were made to the survey in 2017. The first followed the announcement of the UK's planned departure from the European Union in 2019, with a new question introduced regarding the nationalities of respondents' staff members. The second asked respondents to geographically locate percentages of their turnover by UK country.

1.1 Responses

In total, 97 organisations were asked to provide responses; 78 CifA Registered Organisations and 55 FAME members. As most of these organisations are both CifA ROs and members of FAME, the total number of organisations approached is less than the total number of CifA ROs plus FAME members.

The questionnaire sought data that applied on 31st March 2017, the end of financial year 2016-17. Links to the questionnaire were sent to potential respondents on 2nd June 2017, with automated reminder and follow-up emails encouraging completion being sent periodically until the survey closed on 9th July 2017.

A total of 59 responses were received, although five were duplicate entries, so the total number of useable responses was 54, a response rate of 55.7% - a slight decline from the 2016 response rate of 56.4% (the 2015 response rate was 59.6%).

Not every respondent answered every question.

⁴ Aitchison, K. *Archaeological Market Survey 2016*. Landward Research Ltd. <http://landward.org/landward/wp-content/uploads/sites/6/2016/11/Archaeological-Market-Survey-2016.pdf>

⁵ Aitchison, K. *Archaeological Market Survey 2015*. Landward Research Ltd. http://www.landward.eu/Archaeological_Market_Survey_2015.pdf

⁶ Lloyd-James, O. 2017. *The Ninth Report on Local Authority Staff Resources*. Historic England / Association of Local Government Archaeological Officers / Institute of Historic Building Conservation. <https://content.historicengland.org.uk/images-books/publications/ninth-report-la-staff-resources/ninth-report-la-staff-resources.pdf/>

1.2 FAME Membership

is your organisation a member of FAME?

41 of the 53 respondents to this question were FAME members (77% of the respondents, 75% of the FAME membership).

1.3 CifA Registered Organisations

is your organisation a CifA Registered Organisation?

36 of the 51 responses to this question were from CifA Registered Organisations (71% of the respondents). This represented 46% of CifA Registered Organisations.

1.4 Constitution

The questionnaire asked about how respondent organisations were legally constituted. As in previous surveys, the majority of responses came from private limited companies (32 of the 58 respondents to this question). The survey allowed respondents to check as many categories of constitution as applied; four indicated that they were both limited companies and registered charities. This means that the total number of responses for 2017 (54 respondents providing 58 responses) is greater than the number of respondents.

*How is your organisation legally constituted?
please check multiple categories if appropriate*

Constitution	Archaeological Market Survey 2017 March 2017		Archaeological Market Survey 2016 March 2016		Archaeological Market Survey 2015 March 2015	
private limited company (ltd)	33	61%	30	53%	33	62%
registered charity	8	15%	12	21%	13	25%
constituent part of a local planning authority	4	7%	5	9%	7	13%
constituent part of a university	5	9%	8	14%	6	11%
other	8	15%	6	11%	5	9%
public limited company (plc)	0	0%	2	4%	2	4%
total respondents	54		57		53	

Using the numbers of staff reported as being employed on 31st March 2017 (managerial, professional, technical and administrative), the organisations that identify as being registered charities were, on average, the largest organisations in the sector (as was the case in the *Heritage Market Surveys 2016 and 2015*).

staff numbers by organisational legal constitution

Constitution	orgs	total staff	avg staff
registered charity	4	882	220.5
private limited company (Ltd)	33	1315.5	39.9
constituent part of a university	5	195.8	39.2
constituent part of a local planning authority	4	96.8	24.2
other	8	64.5	8.1
public limited company (plc)	0	0	-

(orgs = number of organisations providing both staffing data and information on constitution)

Note that this table includes deliberate double counting – each of the organisations that identified as falling under two categories has been included under both headings; also note that not all organisations provided both information on staffing and their legal constitutions.

The data continue to show (as was the case in 2016 and 2015) that while private limited companies were the most common form of enterprise represented, in this sector more people worked for not-for-distributable profit organisations (registered charities, constituent parts of local planning authorities, constituent parts of universities).

Most of the large employers in this sector had not-for-profit constitutions. This has been identified as a potential barrier to effective competition within a market economy⁷.

⁷ Hinton, P. and Jennings, D. (2007) 'Quality management of archaeology in Great Britain: present practice and future challenges', in Willems, W.J.H. and Van den Dries, M. (eds) *Quality Management in Archaeology*, pp. 100-112, Oxford: Oxbow Books.

1.5 Location of Head and Subsidiary Offices

Respondents were asked about the locations of both their head office and of any subsidiary offices which were being included in their answers.

where is the head office of your organisation located?

head office location	Archaeological Market Survey 2017 March 2017		Archaeological Market Survey 2016 March 2016		Archaeological Market Survey 2015 March 2015	
East Midlands	5	9%	3	5%	5	9%
East of England	7	13%	9	16%	5	9%
Greater London	4	7%	4	7%	6	11%
North East England	1	2%	2	4%	0	0%
North West England	2	4%	4	7%	3	6%
South East England	8	15%	8	14%	8	15%
South West England	8	15%	7	12%	9	17%
West Midlands	4	7%	3	5%	2	4%
Yorkshire and the Humber	4	7%	2	4%	3	6%
Scotland	6	11%	9	16%	5	9%
Wales	3	6%	3	5%	3	6%
Northern Ireland	1	2%	0	0%	1	2%
Outside the UK – in the EU	1	2%	3	5%	3	6%
Outside the UK – not in EU	0	0%				
total	54		57		53	

The reported distribution of head offices has not changed substantially over the period from 2015 to 2017; variation over that time is likely to represent reporting or non-reporting by respondents. There are organisations headquartered in all parts of the UK (and outside the UK) working in the sector.

22 of 54 respondents in 2017 reported having subsidiary offices, comparable with 2016 when 27 of 57 did. The 27 respondents had a total of 49 subsidiary offices – much lower than the 75 subsidiary offices reported in 2016, but this variation is principally due to changes in the specific organisations providing responses.

Of those that reported having subsidiary offices, the numbers of these ranged between one and seven, with an average of 2.5 for each organisation that reported that they had such offices.

are you also answering on behalf of any subsidiary offices? if so, please indicate where they are located?

subsidiary office location	Archaeological Market Survey 2017 March 2017		Archaeological Market Survey 2016 March 2016		Archaeological Market Survey 2015 March 2015	
	East Midlands	4	8%	7	9%	4
East of England	3	6%	7	9%	7	10%
Greater London	2	4%	8	11%	7	10%
North East England	2	4%	4	5%	7	10%
North West England	6	12%	6	8%	5	7%
South East England	6	12%	5	7%	8	11%
South West England	5	10%	8	11%	7	10%
West Midlands	0	0%	9	12%	7	10%
Yorkshire and the Humber	7	14%	8	11%	8	11%
Scotland	8	16%	7	9%	7	10%
Wales	3	6%	4	5%	2	3%
Northern Ireland	0	0%	1	1%	1	1%
outside the UK – in the EU	2	4%	1	1%	1	1%
outside the UK – not in EU	1	2%				
total	49		75		71	

total numbers of offices reported by location

all offices location	head offices	subsidiary offices	total	
East Midlands	5	4	9	9%
East of England	7	3	10	10%
Greater London	4	2	6	6%
North East England	1	2	3	3%
North West England	2	6	8	8%
South East England	8	6	14	14%
South West England	8	5	13	13%
West Midlands	4	0	4	4%
Yorkshire and the Humber	4	7	11	11%
Scotland	6	8	14	14%
Wales	3	3	6	6%
Northern Ireland	1	0	1	1%
outside the UK – in the EU	1	2	3	3%
outside the UK – not in EU	0	1	1	1%
total	54	49	103	

The data cannot be disaggregated in terms of the numbers of individuals working at different offices, so this means that the geographical distribution of staff can only be presented on the basis of the head office locations.

In general, these figures can be seen as an accurate distribution of working archaeologists in the UK, with the highest numbers of archaeologists occurring in the highest areas of general population (Greater London and South-East England). South-West England was also highly represented, with at least one relatively large company being headquartered there.

staff numbers by head office location

location	Archaeological Market Survey 2017 March 2017			Archaeological Market Survey 2016 March 2016			Archaeological Market Survey 2015 March 2015		
	orgs	staff		orgs	staff		orgs	staff	
East Midlands	5	93.4	5%	3	91.2	5%	5	94.6	5%
East of England	6	172.2	8%	4	138.6	7%	4	99.8	5%
Greater London	4	594.6	29%	4	476	25%	5	485	26%
North East England	1	33	2%	2	108	6%	0	0	0%
North West England	2	27	1%	3	25	1%	2	18.5	1%
South East England	6	463.2	23%	5	385.4	20%	7	427.2	23%
South West England	6	307.5	15%	7	429.7	22%	8	352	19%
West Midlands	2	31.6	2%	3	37.8	2%	2	36.3	2%
Yorkshire and the Humber	3	24	1%	1	14	1%	1	19	1%
Scotland	5	224	11%	8	190.9	10%	4	216.3	12%
Wales	2	33	2%	2	16	1%	3	59	3%
Northern Ireland	1	3	<1%	0	0	0%	1	9	<1%
outside the UK – in EU	1	21	1%	0	0	0%	3	48.5	3%
outside the UK – not EU	0	0	0%						
total	44	2027.5		42	1912.6		45	1865.3	

(orgs = numbers of organisations providing staffing data & head office location)

1.6 Years Trading

Respondents were asked when their organisations began trading.

In which year did your organisation begin trading (in applied archaeology)?

started operating	Archaeological Market Survey 2016-17 March 2017		Archaeological Market Survey 2015-16 March 2016		Archaeological Market Survey 2014-15 March 2015	
1900s					1	2%
1910s						
1920s						
1930s						
1940s					1	2%
1950s						
1960s			1	2%	1	2%
1970s	7	13%	8	15%	10	19%
1980s	4	8%	4	7%	7	13%
1990s	17	33%	15	27%	16	30%
2000s	10	19%	15	27%	11	21%
2010s	14	27%	12	22%	6	11%
total	52		55		53	

No respondent organisations were formed before 1970, and the overwhelming majority began trading since 1990. Nearly half of the respondent organisations had been founded since 2000. As was the case in 2016, the median year for starting trading across the 52 respondents was 1999 (half had been trading for at least 18 years, and half less).

Examining the data for trading starts by organisational constitutions, organisations founded in the 1970s are typically both registered charities and limited companies; limited companies have become the preferred model over time, with the majority of organisations founded in the decades since 2000 using this model.

foundation dates by constitutional bases

	plc	ltd company	charity	part of lpa	part of university	other
1970s		4	4	1	1	
1980s		2	1	2		
1990s		7	2	1	3	4
2000s		8			1	1
2010s		10	1			3

(nb some organisations checked more than one constitutional base)

2 STAFF NUMBERS

Respondents were asked about staffing levels on March 31st 2017, covering both UK and non-UK based staff. They were also asked about non-UK based staff, the types of contracts used, relative levels of staff turnover and whether they thought departing staff had left the sector or not. They were also asked for retrospective data to ensure consistency with the previous *Archaeological market survey 2016*.

By comparing like-with-like figures (employment figures provided by individual employers for the numbers of staff they employed in 2017 and 2016), it is estimated that the sectoral workforce (commercial, applied archaeology) grew by a total of 13.2% in the year since the previous survey (by comparison, the sectoral workforce grew by 9.9% in the previous year).

Separately, the number of archaeologists providing curatorial services to local planning authorities (technically, the number of full-time equivalent “archaeological specialists providing advice to local authorities”) in England fell by 3.3% in the year to the beginning of 2016⁸.

No figures are available for the numbers of archaeologists working in “other” contexts (neither commercial nor curatorial), and so those figures have had to be assumed to have remained unchanged.

When figures from these three sources are combined, it is estimated that the entire archaeological profession working in the UK grew over the course of financial year 2016-17 from a total of 5,755 to 6,253 professional archaeologists on 31st March 2017, an increase of 8.7%.

⁸ Lloyd-James, O. 2017. *The Ninth Report on Local Authority Staff Resources*. Historic England / Association of Local Government Archaeological Officers / Institute of Historic Building Conservation.
<https://content.historicengland.org.uk/images-books/publications/ninth-report-la-staff-resources/ninth-report-la-staff-resources.pdf/>

2.1 Employment

The survey asked a series of questions about staffing levels, enquiring about the numbers of staff working on 31st March 2017 and asking how many of them were fee-earners. Respondents were also asked about non-UK based fee-earning staff.

Following the UK government's 2016 decision to take the UK out of the European Union, a new question was introduced regarding the nationalities of staff members, primarily to identify how many were EU citizens.

2.1.1 Total Staff

How many full-time staff were based in your UK offices on 31 March 2017?

Please include all full-time or full-time equivalent staff, together with part-time staff, using estimates of full-time equivalency - for example, a member of staff working 2.5 days a week should be counted as 0.5.

How many UK members of staff (FTE) did your organisation have one year ago, on 31 March 2016 - the census date for the previous Heritage Market Survey?

total UK staff (managerial, professional, technical and administrative)	Archaeological Market Survey 2017 March 2017		Archaeological Market Survey 2016 March 2016		Archaeological Market Survey 2015 March 2015	
	Mar 17	Mar 16	Mar 16	Mar 15	Mar 15	Mar 14
number providing data	48	42	42	42	45	42
total	2110	1772.38	1912.55	1740.41	1865.29	1468.56
average	43.965	42.20	46.65	42.45	41.45	34.97

Data are also presented for comparison purposes that were gathered in the predecessor *Archaeological Market Survey 2016* and the *Archaeological Market Survey 2015* (which both collected directly comparable data from FAME Member Organisations and CIfA Registered Organisations).

Directly comparing data from the 42 organisations that provided data to this survey for both March 2017 and March 2016 shows that their total workforces increased in size by 13.2% in the year between the survey dates (in absolute terms, thirteen had smaller workforces, fourteen had not changed in size and fifteen had grown; these figures show that the total growth has not been evenly distributed, with the companies that grew taking on significantly more staff than the numbers that were lost by the companies that became smaller).

This increase in workforce size – of 13.2% over one year - can be taken as a benchmark for the overall growth of the applied archaeological sector's workforce in 2016-17. This is a significant amount of growth, an increase in the rate of growth reported in 2016 (9.9%).

On this basis, it is estimated that in total 4,351 people were working in the commercial archaeology sector in March 2017.

2.1.2 Staff Nationalities

Of your UK-based staff, how many were:

	Archaeological Market Survey 2017 March 2017	
British (UK subjects)	1,744.05	83%
Nationals of other EU states	305.6	15%
Nationals of other countries (non-UK, non-EU)	40.2	2%
total	2,089.85	

n=45

15% of people working in UK applied archaeology in 2017 are EU citizens; a further 2% of the archaeological workforce are neither from the UK nor the EU.

At the time of the *Profiling the Profession 2012-13* survey⁹, the last time comparable data were gathered, 3% of the entire archaeological workforce's countries of origin were European Union states (other than the UK). A further 4% of the workforce in 2013 were originally from countries in the rest of the world.

2.1.3 Total Fee Earners

As well as being asked about the total numbers of all staff, respondents were also asked about the number of fee-earning staff, defined as "*Fee-earners: members of staff whose time can be billed to clients*".

UK-based fee earners working full-time

total staff	total fee-earners	
2028	1723.12	85.0%

n=41

Data only used from respondents providing positive numbers of staff and of fee-earners.

Fee earners therefore made up 85% of the workforce at the respondent organisations; this is a decrease from the 2016 figure of 94% (and 91% in 2015)

2.1.4 Overseas Staff

Respondents were asked how many of their full-time staff were permanently based overseas on 31st March 2017.

Only two respondents reported having fee-earners based outside the UK, with a total of 20.1 FTE staff. The numbers of fee-earners permanently based outside the UK have varied considerably over the years that these data have been collected, owing to different respondent organisations answering this question each year.

One of the two organisations that identified that they had fee-earners outside the UK reported having more non-UK fee-earners than were based in the UK.

⁹ Aitchison, K. & Rocks-Macqueen, D. 2013. **Archaeology Labour Market Intelligence. Profiling the Profession 2012-13.** <http://www.landward.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/6/2013/10/Archaeology-Labour-Market-Intelligence-Profiling-the-Profession-2012-13.pdf>. Table 81.

Number of fee-earners permanently based outside the UK

	fee-earners outside UK	fee earners in UK (only organisations with non-UK fee earners)	n=
2017	20.1	20.2	2
2016	10.5	253.7	4
2015	21	72	3

2.1.5 Total Employment in UK Archaeology

This is the only part of this report which incorporates data from sources other than the survey of ClfA Registered Organisations and FAME members.

The most recent comprehensive survey of employment in all areas of UK archaeology was *Archaeology Labour Market Intelligence: Profiling the Profession 2012-13*, which incorporated data from *State of the Archaeological Market December 2012*.

Subsequent iterations of the survey of FAME members and ClfA Registered Organisations in 2013-14, 2014-15 and 2015-16 allowed these data to be updated, and now this report presents an updated estimate of the total number of people working in applied, commercial archaeology, which can be combined with the most recent estimates for curatorial archaeology¹⁰ to produce an overall estimate for the entire sector in 2017.

Extrapolating from results received on the assumption that the reporting FAME members and ClfA ROs represent the large part, but not the entirety, of commercial archaeology (as identified in *Profiling the Profession 2012-13*, the last time that data were gathered from non-FAME / ClfA RO operators), this report estimates that 4,351 individuals were working in commercial archaeology in March 2017, an increase of 498 individuals (13.2%) over the period since March 2016. This represents continuing rapid growth in commercial archaeology which the sector has been experiencing from 2014 onwards, and the commercial sector's staffing levels in 2017 are higher than the peak recorded in 2008 (immediately before economic deterioration began to affect the sector in that year).

The most recently published survey of staffing in local planning authorities in England¹¹ considered that the number of archaeologists advising LPAs in England in early 2017 was 262.76, a decrease of 3.3% over the previous year; there is not believed to have been an equivalent rate of change outside England. This represents a loss of 8.9 FTE posts. There are currently fewer people employed in curatorial archaeology than at any time since this series of surveys began. In total, 407 people are considered to be working in curatorial archaeology across the entire UK.

As no new data are available for archaeological employment in "other" sectors, the figures from *Archaeology Labour Market Intelligence: Profiling the Profession 2012-13* (December 2012) are repeated unchanged here.

For all sectors combined there was a net increase of 8.7% in the number of people working in UK archaeology between March 2016 and March 2017.

¹⁰ Lloyd-James, O. 2017. *The Ninth Report on Local Authority Staff Resources*. Historic England / Association of Local Government Archaeological Officers / Institute of Historic Building Conservation.
<https://content.historicengland.org.uk/images-books/publications/ninth-report-la-staff-resources/ninth-report-la-staff-resources.pdf/>

¹¹ *ibid.*

total numbers of archaeologists in employment in the UK, 2007-2017

	Aug 07	Oct 08	Jan 09	Apr 09	Jul 09	Oct 09	Jan 10	Apr 10	Jul 10	Oct 10	Jan 11	Apr 11	Oct 11	Apr 12	Dec 12	Mar 14	Mar 15	Mar 16	Mar 17
curatorial	512	505	505	505	505	505	505	485	485	485	485	442	442	440	485	439	459	416	407
other	2105	2105	2105	2105	2105	2105	2105	2105	2105	2105	2105	2105	2105	2105	1495	1495	1495	1495	1495
commercial	4036	3906	3561	3323	3472	3526	3270	3404	3669	3333	3189	3225	3399	3467	2812	2896	3498	3844	4351
total	6653	6516	6171	5933	6082	6136	5880	5994	6259	5923	5779	5772	5946	6012	4792	4830	5452	5755	6253

In predecessor reports, the total number of “other” posts was left unchanged between the Profiling the Profession census points in August 2007 and December 2012. In this table, the reduction in numbers in this category between those dates has now been distributed to represent steady, progressive change over time rather than as a sudden transformation in December 2012.

Following the global economic downturn of 2008 and an associated loss of jobs in UK archaeology, post-collapse growth in UK archaeological employment began, slowly, in 2013-14, rapidly accelerated in 2014-15 and the sector as a whole has continued to experience rapid growth in staff numbers, driven by the commercial sector, which has continued to add more jobs than are being lost year-on-year in curatorial archaeology.

These curatorial losses are significant, as an overwhelming majority of respondents to this survey, together with surveys conducted in 2014, 2015 and 2016 considered that “a shortage of heritage staff in LPAs is a major constraint on heritage projects” (7, *Perceptions* below). Since 2011, the number of curatorial posts has decreased by 19%. However, commercial archaeology has continued to grow despite this perceived constraint.

2.2 Contracts

how many of your members of staff were working on each of the following types of contract or agreement on 31 March 2017?

	full-time		part-time		total	
permanent	1369.65	92.7%	108.3	7.3%	1477.95	76.7%
fixed term	386	97.5%	10	2.6%	396	20.5%
casual	13	92.9%	1	7.1%	14	0.7%
volunteer	0	0.00%	40	100.0%	40	2.1%
total	1768.65	91.7%	159.3	8.3%	1927.95	

n=43 (nb – percentages read horizontally across rows, not vertically down columns, except for total column)

Data were received on staff contracts from 43 respondents, relating to the contracts or working agreements held by over 1900 employees or volunteers.

Over three-quarters of staff were on permanent contracts, just over 20% on fixed term (temporary) contracts, very few were 'casual' staff or volunteers were reported. These figures are very similar to the results in 2016 and 2015.

92% of employees were on full-time contracts, and 77% of those people were permanently engaged. Part-time workers were also more likely to have permanent contracts than to be working on fixed-term contracts.

Please note the discrepancy between the total number of staff calculated on the basis of reported contracts and the figure reported under 3.1.1, *Total Staff* above is because fewer respondents provided data on whether staff were on full-or part-time contracts.

In comparison with the equivalent data from 2015-16 (below), the overall percentage of staff who were on permanent contracts remained almost unchanged, as was the case when comparing 2015 with 2014. This supports the view that the ongoing increase in jobs seen since 2014-15 and continued in 2015-16 and 2016-17 was not simply a response to an increase in short-term fieldwork, as that would likely be represented by a disproportionate increase in the percentage of fixed-term posts (the 2016 figures are presented below for comparison).

how many of your members of staff were on each of the following types of contract on 31 March 2016?

	full-time		part-time		Total	
permanent	1107	91.6%	102	8.4%	1209	73.9%
fixed term	340	92.6%	27	7.4%	367	22.4%
casual	35	81.4%	8	18.6%	43	2.6%
volunteer	3	18.8%	13	81.3%	16	1.0%
total	1485	90.8%	150	9.2%	1635	

n=38 from Archaeological Market Survey 2016

2.3 Staff Turnover

Respondents were asked about the relative (not absolute) levels of staff turnover in the period since the previous survey.

What level of staff turnover did you experience between 31 March 2016 and 31 March 2017?

Staff turnover	Archaeological Market Survey 2017 March 2017		Archaeological Market Survey 2016 March 2016		Archaeological Market Survey 2015 March 2015	
none (all current staff were working for us one year ago)	0	0%	13	33%	6	13%
some (up to 10% of current staff were not working for us one year ago)	3	43%	11	28%	21	47%
moderate (up to 25% of current staff were not working for us one year ago)	2	29%	11	28%	10	22%
considerable (over 25% of current staff were not working for us one year ago)	2	29%	5	13%	8	18%
total	7		40		45	

The number of respondents providing data on staff turnover (or absence of turnover) dropped considerably in 2016-17.

It is possible that the low level of response to this question stemmed from both the growth of the sector may have meant that few people moved from one employer to another, and that where organisations had expanded, with new staff joining, respondents had disregarded this question (as might be suggested by two of the comments to 2.4, Staff Lost From the Sector, below).

2.4 Staff Lost From the Sector

Respondents were asked whether they believed that staff who had formerly worked for them were still working in archaeology or not.

If you lost staff in the period between 31 March 2016 and 31 March 2017, do you believe that these people left the profession or stayed within it with different employers?

staff destinations	Archaeological Market Survey 2017 March 2017		Archaeological Market Survey 2016 March 2016		Archaeological Market Survey 2015 March 2015	
all found alternative employment within archaeology	1	14%	1	4%	10	29%
most found alternative employment within archaeology	3	43%	16	67%	14	40%
even split between leaving the profession and finding alternative employment within archaeology	2	29%	4	17%	6	17%
most left the profession	0	0%	0	0%	2	6%
all left the profession	1	14%	3	13%	3	9%
total	7		24		35	

As was the case in 2016 and 2015, most respondents thought that all, or most, of the people who had left their employ were still working in archaeology but for different employers, which continues to repeat a pattern previously identified, emphasising that a major component of staff turnover is made up of people moving within the sector.

Comments received:

1 left the profession
Business is currently closing down, explaining the drop in staff over last year
Most of the turnover has been new staff joining
One member of staff retired
We had hardly any leavers - the turned over staff are new joiners

2.5 Salaries

Respondents were asked whether salaries had typically risen or fallen during the 2016-17 financial year. This was specifically not a question about total salary bills, as those would be directly influenced by the number of personnel on the payroll.

did salaries at your organisation typically rise or fall between March 2016 and March 2017? (NB - not total salary bill)

when comparing changes to inflation, please consider the rate of inflation at the date of the salary settlement

salary changes	Archaeological Market Survey 2017 March 2017		Archaeological Market Survey 2016 March 2016		Archaeological Market Survey 2015 March 2015	
rose by above inflation	0	0%	22	54%	24	53%
rose by inflation	4	57%	12	29%	9	20%
unchanged	2	29%	7	17%	11	24%
fell by up to 10%	1	14%	0	0%	0	0%
fell by over 10%	0	0%	0	0%	1	2%
total	7		41		45	

Very few respondents answered this question. From this limited base, it can be seen that for the third year in succession, the majority of respondents reported salaries as having risen by inflation or above. The CPI rate of inflation in March 2017 was 2.3%¹²; respondents were asked to compare changes with inflation at the date of the salary settlement.

As the sample size is so small, examining the average sizes of the workforce at the organisations where data on salary changes are available has relatively little value. The data for 2016 are presented below for comparison.

salary changes March 2017	organisations	individuals	average size of workforce
rose by above inflation	0	0	0
rose by inflation	4	495	123.75
unchanged	2	4	2
fell by up to 10%	1	0.75	0.75
fell by over 10%	0	0	0

salary changes March 2016	organisations	individuals	average size of workforce
rose by above inflation	22	1546.55	70.30
rose by inflation	12	293.27	24.44
unchanged	6	44.9	7.48
fell by up to 10%	0	0	0
fell by over 10%	0	0	0

¹² <http://www.rateinflation.com/inflation-rate/uk-historical-inflation-rate> accessed 11th August 2017

2.6 Charge-out Rates

Respondents were asked about any changes to their charge-out rates in the year ending 31st March 2017, and then about how they anticipated they would change in the next year.

How did your charge out rates change in the year to the end of March 2017?

- *by what percentage did your charge-out rates increase (+) or decrease (-) over the year ending 31 March 2017?*
- *by what percentage did you or do you anticipate that your rates will increase (+) or decrease (-) over the year ending 31 March 2018?*

	reported change to March 2017	anticipated change to March 2017 (reported in 2016)	anticipated change to March 2018
range	-5% to 10%	-10% to 20%	0% to 10%
mean	3.1%	4.3%	3.0%
median	2.5%	5.0%	2.0%
mode	0% (10 responses)	5.0% (10 responses)	0% (12 responses)
<i>n=</i>	39	35	39

Charge-out rates rose by an average of 3.1% in the year to March 2017; a year previously, they had been expected to rise by 4.3% (this is consistent with the previous pattern, where the average increases in charge-out rates have consistently been less than were anticipated a year before). Looking forward, respondents expect their charge-out rates to rise by 3.0% in the year to March 2018.

The March 2017 annual UK inflation rate (CPI) was 2.3%¹³; 51% of respondents (20 of 39) increased their charge-out rates in 2016-17 by more than this amount.

¹³ <http://www.rateinflation.com/inflation-rate/uk-historical-inflation-rate> accessed 11th August 2017

3 FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE

Respondents were asked a series of questions about their organisation's financial performance in financial year 2016-17 and expectations. It was recognised that some respondents might be reluctant to release such information (even though the responses were anonymous).

- Overall, the financial performance statistics suggest that the sector may be approaching maximum capacity – it had not grown in terms of turnover in 2016-17, despite staff complements increasing (meaning productivity was falling), and profit levels had stabilised.
- The sector had positive future financial expectations – although these expectations were not as ambitious as they had been one year before.
- Average financial turnovers decreased from 2015-16 to 2016-17.
- Reported profit (or surplus) levels stabilised at the same levels as the previous year, but continued to be relatively low.
- More than 80% of income was generated from the private sector; this has continued to increase in importance year-on-year.
- In terms of business activity, work generated by residential development continued to very clearly be the biggest market sector.

3.1 Turnover

What was your annual turnover (in £) in financial year 2016-17?

Please enter full numbers of pounds, e.g. 1250000, not decimal fractions of millions etc

if your accounting period does not run from April to March, please indicate fee income for nearest 12-month period for which audited figures are available, making clear which period they cover.

- *your UK turnover in year ending 31 March 2017*
- *your turnover from non-UK sources (including Republic of Ireland) in year ending 31 March 2017*

	range	mean	median	n=
UK turnover	£33,000 to £13,500,000	£2,348,383	£643,500	32
non-UK turnover	£0 to £80,000	£5,318	£0	33; 29 reported zero return

2016 figures (from Archaeological Market Survey 2016)

	range	mean	median	n=
UK turnover	£15,100 to £12,484,000	£2,928,146	£755,618	24
non-UK turnover	£0 to £150,000	£48,219	£0	25; 20 reported zero return

Respondent organisations typically turned over £643,500 in 2016-17 (half generated more than this amount of revenue, half less). For most respondents, none of this income was generated outside the UK.

The average (mean) UK turnover for an applied archaeology company in 2016-17 was £2.35m, a decrease of 19.8% on the figure reported for 2015-16 (although it must be noted that the 2015-16 figures represented a calculated 55.7% increase on the year before; this

reported high levels of turnover and of profitability suggest that 2015-16 may have been an abnormal year).

It should also be noted that the decrease in the median figure was 14.8%.

UK turnover	2016-17		2015-16	
<£250,000	8	25%	5	20%
£250,000 -> £500,000	4	13%	3	12%
£500,000 -> £1m	8	25%	7	28%
£1m -> £2.5m	6	19%	3	12%
£2.5m -> £5m	1	3%	0	0%
£5m -> £10m	2	6%	4	16%
>=£10m	3	9%	3	12%
total	32		25	

Multiplying the mean figure by the total survey population (of 97 organisations) would suggest that in 2016-17 the sector generated £228m of revenue; the comparable figure for 2015-16 was £296m.

	annual (UK) turnover			source
	n=	mean	change	
2016-17	32	£2.35m	-19.8%	Archaeological Market Survey 2017 March 2017
2015-16	24	£2.93m	+55.7%	Archaeological Market Survey 2016 March 2016
2014-15	37	£1.88m	+14.5%	Archaeological Market Survey 2015 March 2015
2013-14	20	£1.64m		Heritage Market Survey 2014 March 2014
2012-13	no data available			
2011-12	33	£1.71m	-6.6%	State of the Archaeological Market December 2012
2010-11	32	£1.83m	-4.2%	State of the Archaeological Market December 2012
2009-10	32	£1.91m		State of the Archaeological Market December 2012

How was this income distributed by clients' or funders' locations within the UK?

	total	%	number of respondents with funding from that country
England	£66,648,128	88.4%	28
Scotland	£5,511,650	7.3%	7
Wales	£3,163,071	4.2%	9
Northern Ireland	£5,400	<0.1%	1
total	£66,468,128		<i>n=32</i>

Most companies did not generate any non-UK income, but those that did generated 0.6% of turnover from those sources.

On average, respondents typically expected their turnover to increase by 2.5% in 2017-18; the average expectations for 2016-17 were for increase in turnover of 10.8%, and the 2015-16 expectation was for an increase of 7.6%.

predicted % change in turnover between years ending 31 March 2017 and 31 March 2018

	range	mean	median	n=
anticipated change	-90% to 33%	+2.5%	+5.0%	32

31 organisations provided data for both financial turnover and numbers of staff; on average these organisations employed 53.1 members of staff each, with an average turnover per staff member of £45,309, a decrease from 2015-16 of 0.7%. Financial turnover per member of staff is a proxy measure of productivity.

average turnover per member of staff	
2016-17	£45,309
2015-16	£45,615
2014-15	£45,914
2013-14	£56,237
2012-13	no data available
2011-12	£53,271

23 respondents provided data on their contributions to the community, public archaeology and education which had not been paid for directly by a client. On average these contributions were £26,545, an increase of 3.2% on from the 2015-16 figure of £25,728.

These contributions equated to 0.9% of those organisations' average annual turnovers (matching the calculated figure of 0.9% for 2015-16).

your contribution to the community, public archaeology and education which has not been paid for directly by a client

	range	mean	median	n=
non-client contributions	£500 - £120,000	£26,545	£5,000	32; 9 reported zero returns

3.2 Profit Levels

Respondents were asked about the levels of profit (or surplus, for not-for-profit enterprises) realised in financial year 2016-7.

your surplus (plus or minus) in the year ending 31 March 2017

	range	mean	% of mean turnover	median	n=
surplus 2016-17	-£286,000 to £1,000,000	£121,252	5.2%	£43,000	31
surplus 2015-16	-£75,000 to £799,000	£154,438	5.2%	£50,000	23

Profit levels decreased in 2016-17 when compared with the year before in terms of the average absolute levels of profit, but remained unchanged in terms of that as an average percentage of turnover. Historically, profit levels had increased to 5.2% in 2015-16 from 2.5% in 2014-15 and 1.9% in 2013-14.

In 2015-16 it was recognised that nearly 30% of respondents had reported profit levels over 10% which was considered to be a high rate of profitability, indicating that the sector had the resources to start investing and developing. In 2016-17, the percentage of respondents reporting these levels of profitability had increased.

While most respondents reported being in profit, three of the 31 organisations responding in 2017 reported negative figures, representing absolute losses, with another three reporting neither surplus nor loss.

level of profit as % of turnover (surplus)	Archaeological Market Survey 2017 March 2017		Archaeological Market Survey 2016 March 2016		Archaeological market survey 2015 March 2015	
>25%	1	3%	3	14%	0	0%
10-25%	13	41%	3	14%	4	12%
5-10%	4	13%	4	19%	6	18%
<5%	14	44%	11	52%	23	70%
Total	32		21		33	

Data only used from respondents providing turnover and profit/surplus figures

3.3 Funding Sources (areas of activity as turnover)

Please estimate your UK turnover from the following sources in the year ending 31 March 2017

	n=	total	mean	%	2016%
central government departments and agencies	16	£5,340,700	£333,794	7%	3%
other public bodies (including universities, public-private partnerships and local enterprise partnerships)	20	£1,398,100	£69,905	2%	4%
community groups (including HLF projects, town and parish councils and neighbourhood forums)	19	£1,501,440	£79,023	2%	5%
district, county or unitary councils (local planning authorities)	22	£3,650,900	£165,950	5%	3%
national agencies (HE/EH, HES, Cadw etc)	23	£2,256,900	£98,126	3%	6%
private sector clients (including third parties)	31	£62,297,309	£2,009,591	81%	79%
aggregate total		£76,445,349			

Of 31 respondents to this question, most had secured some income from each of the six defined areas of funding and all had received funding from private sector clients, which represented the overwhelming majority (81%) of the total estimated income reported; this was an increase on the 2016 figure of 79%, which in turn was an increase on the 2015 figure of 75%.

In comparison with 2015-16, the distribution of funding sources has remained broadly constant, although the percentage of funds received from central government departments and (non-heritage) agencies increased while funding from community groups including HLF projects and from national heritage agencies fell.

3.4 Market Sectors

The survey sought detailed information on which market sectors were generating income for the respondent organisations.

Please do not include non-UK turnover in this section

In the column headed "UK income", please indicate your UK income in the year ending 31 March 2017 for the work in each of the sectors listed.

To avoid double counting, please do not include fee income from any commission in more than one box. The total for this column must not exceed total fee income reported under turnover in the question above. If you are unsure about which sector to attribute a particular commission to, please refer to the Note to Respondents below.

category	total	% 2017	% 2016	range	average	n=
residential development	£22,311,306	41.7%	53.4%	£1,508 - £7,431,000	£1,174,279	19
commercial and industrial	£9,596,060	17.9%	13.5%	£15,000 - £5,000,000	£738,158	13
any other services not categorised above	£4,688,987	8.8%	0.6%	£1,007 - £3,424,100	£520,999	5
transport	£3,432,755	6.4%	10.3%	£5,000 - £1,800,000	£228,850	14
Energy	£3,058,835	5.7%	3.0%	£5,000 - £1,318,000	£278,076	10
leisure, sport, entertainment and tourism	£2,894,740	5.4%	0.2%	£20,000 - £85,000	£241,228	12
community projects and HLF	£1,663,821	3.1%	2.1%	£9381 - £1,200,000	£127,986	13
retail and town centres	£977,915	1.8%	2.9%	£2,775 - £400,000	£97,792	10
water supply	£972,480	1.8%	2.4%	£50,000 - £669,600	£138,926	5
minerals	£844,618	1.6%	2.5%	£20,000 - £197,600	£70,385	10
other research and public archaeology	£683,440	1.3%	0.5%	£12,000 - £500,000	£113,907	8
education	£584,602	1.1%	1.4%	£5,000 - £204,200	£53,146	10
heritage conservation	£548,791	1.0%	1.5%	£10,000 - £257,200	£91,465	6
national agencies and university grants	£500,000	0.9%	2.2%	£5,000 - £300,000	£71,429	4
Health	£345,640	0.6%	1.2%	£5,000 - £204,200	£43,205	6
assistance to LPAs in delivering development control services	£156,440	0.3%	0.2%	£70,000	£26,073	3
local authority initiatives	£107,302	0.2%	0.7%	£7,302 - £100,000	£21,460	2
waste	£92,330	0.2%	1.4%	£13,000 - £500,000	£15,388	3

telecommunications	£45,000	0.1%	0.0%	£5,000 - £25,000	£6,429	3
aggregate total	£53,505,062					

Residential development continued to represent the largest market sector by far, but as an aggregate percentage had dropped from 53.4% of income in 2015-16 to 41.7% in 2016-17. The second largest market sector continued to be commercial and industrial; these two sectors combined represented nearly 60% of the reported revenue of the respondent organisations.

There was a marked increase in the relative importance of the catchall “any other services...” category, and also of “leisure, sport, entertainment and tourism” – in both cases, these were the result of single respondents having particularly high revenues from the sectors.

Respondents were also asked about turnover change by market sector. The question simply asked whether turnover had increased, decreased or was unchanged for each market sector, and what expectations were for the following year.

In the table below, the figures are aggregated results for each market sector, so they represent measures of sentiment – for example, a figure of +100% would mean that every respondent considered that turnover had increased in that sector, while a figure of 0% means that the number reporting (or expecting) growth in a market sector was exactly balanced by the number expecting decline.

In the two columns headed “2016-17” and “2017-18” please indicate whether your turnover in the UK market for each of the sectors listed grew, declined or was unchanged from the previous year in 2016-17 and whether you think it will grow, decline or be unchanged in 2017-18.

category	2016-17 reported		2017-18 Predicted	
	%	count	%	count
residential development	+50%	20	+39%	18
commercial and industrial	+33%	15	+13%	15
retail and town centres	+10%	10	+44%	9
leisure, sport, entertainment and tourism	+8%	12	±0%	11
minerals	+9%	11	+27%	11
waste	±0%	7	0%	7
transport	+20%	15	+92%	13
energy	+45%	11	-8%	12
telecommunications	+13%	8	-11%	9
water supply	±0%	8	±0%	9
education	+20%	10	±0%	10
health	+13%	8	-11%	9
community projects and HLF	+23%	13	+23%	13
national agencies and university grants	±0%	7	-14%	7
local authority initiatives	+33%	6	-14%	7
other research and public archaeology	+17%	6	+33%	6
heritage conservation	+17%	6	+29%	7
assistance to LPAs in delivering development control services	+29%	7	±0%	7
any other services not categorised above	+30%	10	+9%	11

Very substantial numbers of respondents anticipate growth in 2017-18 in residential development, retail and town centres – and above all, in transport, with a near universal expectation of increased work deriving from transport development which can largely be attributed to anticipated work on or relating to HS2.

4 FORMS OF CONTRACT

Which forms of client contract do you routinely use?

Check as many as apply

	n=	% of respondents using
exchange of letters / emails	19	70%
your own organisation's standard t&c	19	70%
client's standard t&c	16	59%
bespoke	13	48%
NEC3 (various – family of contracts)	7	26%
ICE (short form or alternative)	6	22%
none	2	7%
other	0	0%

n=27

27 respondents answered this question, most of which used more than one form of contract. The two respondent that checked "none" also checked several other forms.

Externally standardised approaches (the Institution of Civil Engineers' NEC3 or ICE short form) were less frequently used than exchanges of letters, client or contractors' own standard terms and conditions, or bespoke forms of client contract.

5 BUSINESS CONFIDENCE

The sector grew in terms of workforce in 2016-17 while reporting reduced average financial turnover, with indications that business confidence peaked in 2015 and has steadily declined since.

Historically, in 2015 the sector was more confident than it had been at any time since 2008 (the start of this data collection exercise), but since then (following both the Brexit referendum of June 2016 and the General Election of June 2017), levels of confidence have declined.

In 2017, confidence was still high, but confidence was decreasing when compared with one year before (when, in turn, the sector was not as confident as it had been in 2015).

- While respondents overwhelmingly expected to maintain or increase their staff levels in the next year, they were not as confident of doing so as they had been in 2016.
- While there was overall confidence that market conditions would not deteriorate in 2017-18, the sector was not as confident about the future as it had been one year before, and confidence had been declining since 2015.
- More respondents expect there to be no business failures in the sector than expected some, and feelings in this area were more positive than they had been in 2016
- Respondents generally did not expect to expand their business in 2017-18. While overall business confidence peaked in 2015, the level of expectation of business expansion reached its peak in 2014.

5.1 Staffing Levels

At the end of March 2017, did you anticipate any changes to your staffing levels over the next year (to 31 March 2017)?

change in staffing	Archaeological Market Survey 2017 March 2017		Archaeological Market Survey 2016 March 2016		Archaeological Market Survey 2015 March 2015	
increase staff numbers	13	48%	15	60%	23	62%
maintain staff numbers	10	37%	9	36%	11	30%
lower staff numbers	4	15%	1	4%	3	8%
total	27	+33%	25	+56%	37	+54%

Don't know or no answer excluded

Comments received:

Business is closing down
I am sole trader.
I do not have a glass ball
I have no plans to employ anyone other than myself
increase by 30%
Maintain or increase
Provided capacity is available.
Recruiting at all levels in the SE and Midlands
Stable core staff; increase in fixed term contract

From April 2012 to March 2016, the proportion of respondents who expected to maintain or increase staff levels increased with every iteration of this survey.

In 2016-17, while the majority of respondents do still expect to either maintain or increase their staff numbers, overall the sector is not as confident of retaining staff as it was at the time of the previous survey in 2016.

Note the graph below represents the proportion of respondents that expected to either increase or maintain their staff numbers, minus the number of respondents that expected to lose staff – so positive results mean staff numbers are not expected to fall.

5.2 Market Conditions

On 31 March 2017, did you believe that market conditions would deteriorate over the next 12 months? (to 31 March 2018)

market conditions	Archaeological Market Survey 2017 March 2017		Archaeological Market Survey 2016 March 2016		Archaeological Market Survey 2015 March 2015	
the market will deteriorate	7	26%	6	21%	3	8%
the market will not deteriorate	15	56%	18	64%	31	84%
don't know	5	19%	4	14%	3	8%
total	27	+30%	28	+43%	37	+76%

In the 2014-15 survey, the sector was extremely confident that market conditions would not deteriorate in 2015-16; this view was tempered considerably in 2015-16, and confidence

reduced further in 2016-17. However, a significant majority of respondents still thought that the market would not deteriorate in the coming year.

Comments received:

Absolutely not
although this view assumed that large infrastructure
Brexit impact on business confidence; delays to govt infrastructure programme
house building still strong
Housing may deteriorate; but infrastructure should increase
Impact from Brexit negotiation uncertainty
No option for yes and no - some markets will improve others will decline
While some sectors may slow or contract, infrastructure will drive high levels of demand.
Will depend on government policy and willingness to invest in development to maintain economic growth. There is sufficient planned development to keep everyone busy so that is a cause for optimism; however things are undoubtedly fragile with any number of crises on the horizon which could have a sudden and devastating effect on the economy and/or archaeological work

In every survey since December 2012, more respondents have considered that market conditions would improve than would deteriorate, and overall confidence in the sector's market conditions had been increasing from September 2011 until March 2015, which represented a high-point of confidence. Since 2015, confidence in future market conditions has steadily declined.

5.3 Businesses Ceasing Trading

From the start of this series of surveys in 2008 until 2014, more respondents expected some archaeological practices to cease trading in the next 12 months than did not. In the earliest iterations of the survey, an overwhelming – near universal – majority of respondents expected that this would happen.

In March 2015, for the first time in this series of surveys, more respondents did not believe that any businesses would fail than did; this was still the case in March 2016, and in 2017 businesses were more confident that no archaeological practices will cease trading in the next 12 months than they had been one year before.

At the end of March 2017, did you expect any archaeological practices to cease trading over the next 12 months?

businesses ceasing trading	Archaeological Market Survey 2017 March 2017		Archaeological Market Survey 2016 March 2016		Archaeological Market Survey 2015 March 2015	
yes	6	23%	7	26%	6	16%
no	14	54%	10	37%	21	57%
don't know	6	23%	10	37%	10	27%
total	26	+31%	27	+11%	37	+41%

The title of the graph below emphasises that positive figures reflect an expectation that no businesses in the sector will fail in the next year.

Comments received:

Normal wastage from organisations unable to make a return.
not sure if any did but there are certainly some outfits with poor business sense, poor employment conditions and shoddy work that probably should have no place in a modern professional world
Sustainability is not built into every organization's cost plan; charge-out rates can be insufficient and fixed price set cost of job too low; contract penalties; business strategy for larger organizations to let subsidiary companies go into receivership
This is statistically the case
We know that one went into administration but this is unlikely to be as a result of market conditions!

5.4 Expansion

Respondents were asked about planning for future business expansion.

Did you have any plans to expand your business significantly over twelve months from March 2017 (e.g. in premises, vehicles, capital equipment)?

expansion plans	Archaeological Market Survey 2017 March 2017		Archaeological Market Survey 2016 March 2016		Archaeological Market Survey 2015 March 2015	
yes	10	38%	12	50%	21	57%
no	15	58%	10	42%	15	41%
don't know	1	4%	2	8%	1	3%
total	26	-20%	24	+8%	37	+16%

For the first time since December 2012, more respondents were not planning for business expansion in the next year than were.

Relative enthusiasm for business expansion peaked at the time of the March 2014 survey, and has steadily declined since.

Historically, future expansion plans have mapped well against the reality of changes in staff numbers; the sentiment expressed for expansion began to become more positive than negative in March 2012, and the data collected from the next survey (December 2012) showed that the sector had started re-growing from that point onwards.

March 2014 represented a peak in positive expectations for the year ahead, and in 2014-15 staff numbers increased by more than at any other survey period. In March 2015, expectations were still positive, but more modest – and staff numbers did continue to increase in the next year, but not at the rate experienced in 2014-15.

Because expansion plans are slowing does not automatically mean that there will be a reduction in staff numbers in the next year, but it is an indicator of the cautiousness of the sector at the point of the survey.

Comments received:

30% growth
All of the above are likely
But workload indicated short-term growth in staff numbers
Forward plan assumes 20% growth
There are plans to invest if we can (it is years since we have been able to). Much depends on how confident we become around increasing surplus and meeting income targets

6 SKILLS, TRAINING AND QUALIFICATIONS

The survey sought to identify which areas of skills were being lost from the sector, where skills were being bought in (skills shortages) and where organisations were seeking to address the issue through training (skills gaps).

Throughout this part of the report, figures relate to the respondents who have experienced a particular, specific change in the previous year as a percentage of all who responded to each general question. For example, in 2016-17, 12 respondents had lost skills in some way in the previous year; of these, 7 had lost fieldwork skills, so the percentage presented is 58% (7/12). This does not mean that 58% of fieldwork skills have been lost from the sector, nor does it mean that 58% of all organisations in commercial archaeology lost fieldwork skills.

Respondents were also asked in general terms whether they considered there were particular areas with skills problems across the sector.

6.1 Areas of Skills Losses

For the first time since this survey series began in 2008, fieldwork skills were not the area where skills loss was most frequently identified (although 50% of respondents to this question did report losing skills in this area).

Desk-based or environmental assessment was the area where most respondents identified that they had lost skills.

This switch to pre-fieldwork skills being the area where companies are most likely to lose skills is significant, as it can be interpreted as meaning respondents are generally retaining or expanding their fieldwork skills base, but struggling to retain the desk-based research and assessment skills. On the assumption that skills are largely lost by members of staff moving to different employers, it suggests that there is increasing competition for both desk-based assessment skills and for skilled fieldworkers.

In the twelve months to the end of March 2017, did your organisation lose skills in any of these areas?

	Archaeological Market Survey 2017 March 2017		Archaeological Market Survey 2016 March 2016		Archaeological Market Survey 2015 March 2015	
desk-based or environmental assessment	7	58%	4	36%	5	28%
fieldwork (invasive or non-invasive)	6	50%	6	55%	13	72%
post-fieldwork analysis	4	33%	4	36%	6	33%
advice to clients	3	25%	1	9%	4	22%
data management	2	17%	2	18%	4	22%
artefact or ecofact conservation	2	17%	2	18%	1	6%
other	0	0%	1	9%	2	11%
total respondents	12		11		18	

6.2 Areas of Skills Buy-in

As in 2016 and 2015, many more respondents reported buying-in skills than had reported losing them. These are areas of skills shortages, skills that an organisation does not have but that it buys in from external providers.

Both fieldwork and conservation skills were bought in by nearly two-thirds of respondents, and post-fieldwork analysis was bought in by nearly half. In 2016, post-fieldwork analysis had been the skill most frequently bought in, and in 2017 nearly half of the respondents who bought in skills did so in this area.

The continuing high levels of demand for fieldwork and post-fieldwork skills are linked to the high levels of fieldwork activity being undertaken.

While desk-based or environmental assessment was identified as the skills area being lost most often, very few respondents were buying this in to backfill for those losses – so this was not being perceived as a skills shortage,

This series of surveys has consistently shown over time that artefact or ecofact conservation is a skill that is normally bought in from external providers. Conservation was rarely reported as a skill being lost by employers, because this was now very much the norm to be provided by external providers – although there was increasing demand for training in this area, suggesting either that companies want to bring this back in-house or that external capacity to provide this was beginning to be stretched.

In the twelve months to the end of March 2017, did your organisation have to buy-in skills in any of these areas?

skills bought in	Archaeological Market Survey 2017 March 2017		Archaeological Market Survey 2016 March 2016		Archaeological Market Survey 2015 March 2015	
	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage
artefact or ecofact conservation	16	64%	14	56%	19	61%
fieldwork (invasive or non-invasive)	16	64%	14	56%	10	32%
post-fieldwork analysis	12	48%	16	64%	16	52%
Other	4	16%	6	24%	3	10%
data management	3	12%	1	4%	5	16%
desk-based or environmental assessment	3	12%	5	20%	2	6%
providing advice to clients	2	8%	3	12%	0	0%
total respondents	25		25		31	

“other” skills reported as being bought in:

HR, Financial, Training

Scientific dating (C14), medieval pottery

6.3 Areas of Training

Areas where organisations address skills deficits by investing in training their staff are skills gaps.

As was the case in 2016, the majority of respondents that invested in training invested in developing their team's fieldwork, post-fieldwork analysis and desk-based / environmental assessment skills, the three areas where skills were most commonly being reported as being lost (so therefore these were skills gaps, skills that existing staff needed but lacked, that were being tackled by investment in training).

As has been seen in each survey since 2014, a much higher proportion of FAME members and Cifa Registered Organisations have been investing in training while they were simultaneously increasing the number of people on their payrolls.

When areas of skills training are compared to the areas where outside expertise was being bought in (skills shortages – where employers cannot find staff with the relevant skills), fieldwork and post-fieldwork skills are being both bought in and internally trained up.

Desk-based or environmental assessment and providing advice to clients are much more likely to be areas where staff will be trained than outside expertise bought in, and although there was increasing investment in training for conservation in 2017, it continues to be much more likely to be bought in.

In the twelve months to the end of March 2017 did your organisation invest in skills training in any of these areas?

training investment	Archaeological Market Survey 2017 March 2017		Archaeological Market Survey 2016 March 2016		Archaeological Market Survey 2015 March 2015	
fieldwork (invasive or non-invasive)	16	67%	17	68%	20	65%
post-fieldwork analysis	16	67%	15	60%	14	45%
desk-based or environmental assessment	15	63%	14	56%	17	55%
providing advice to clients	10	42%	8	32%	9	29%
data management	9	38%	8	32%	14	45%
artefact or ecofact conservation	8	33%	5	20%	9	29%
Other	4	17%	8	32%	5	16%
total respondents	24		25		31	

The following 'other' skills were identified as having been areas where organisations invested in training:

Contract Management and Health and Safety Advice
H&S training, management training
Public Enquiry training

6.4 Skills Issues Across the Sector

Respondents were asked about their perceptions of skills issues across the archaeological sector. The phrase “skills shortages” was used here in the questionnaire; this can have a technical definition relating to a problem skills area that is addressed through bringing in external expertise, but here was considered to refer to areas where there is a general under-provision of skilled labour.

Respondents identified fieldwork skills as being the area where most consider that there are skills issues across the sector, followed by post-fieldwork analysis. As in 2016 and 2015, these have been the key areas of concern, potentially reflecting difficulties recruiting during the ongoing fieldwork boom.

On 31 March 2017, did you think there were skills shortages across archaeological practice in any of these areas?

skills issues	Archaeological Market Survey 2017 March 2017		Archaeological Market Survey 2016 March 2016		Archaeological Market Survey 2015 March 2015	
	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage
fieldwork (invasive or non-invasive)	17	74%	11	55%	18	67%
post-fieldwork analysis	13	57%	13	65%	15	56%
artefact or ecofact conservation	11	48%	7	35%	8	30%
providing advice to clients	10	43%	7	35%	8	30%
desk-based or environmental assessment	6	26%	7	35%	9	33%
data management	4	17%	3	15%	3	11%
other	3	13%	7	35%	5	19%
total respondents	23		20		27	

“Other” areas where skills issues were identified:

Contract Management and Health and Safety Advice
Generally there is quite a low skills set across the board
Project Management

Respondent organisations’ views on skills issues across the sector continue to closely match what they can identify within their own organisations – and so sector-wide skills issues mirror individual organisations’ training needs. In 2016-17, fieldwork and post-fieldwork skills were the areas where many organisations invested in training, and these were the areas where skills issues were recognised across the sector.

This is very definitely a positive state of affairs, whereby employers are recognising and then taking responsibility for addressing skills issues, rather than leaving them for outside bodies.

6.5 NVQ

The National Vocational Qualification in Archaeological Practice was first awarded in 2009 (the formal title for this qualification is now the *Level 3 NVQ Certificate in Archaeological Practice*). Respondents were asked about whether they had previously supported a member of staff gaining such a qualification, and whether they would consider doing so in the future.

On 31 March 2017, had you or were you considering supporting a member of staff to gain a vocational qualification in archaeological practice (NVQ)?

NVQ support	Archaeological Market Survey 2017 March 2017				Archaeological Market Survey 2016 March 2016				Archaeological Market Survey 2015 March 2015			
	have supported		would consider in future		have supported		would consider in future		have supported		would consider in future	
yes	7	33%	12	75%	8	31%	13	54%	15	60%	11	34%
no	14	67%	3	19%	18	69%	7	29%	3	12%	21	66%
don't know	0	0%	1	6%	0	0%	4	17%	7	28%	0	0%
total	21		16		26		24		25		32	

Levels of support for the NVQ in Archaeological Practice from FAME members and CifA Registered Organisations remain high, with a relative increase in the proportion of respondents who were prepared to consider supporting a candidate in the future.

6.6 Apprenticeship

On 31 March 2017, had you or were you considering supporting a member of staff to undertake an Apprenticeship in Historic Environment Practice?

Apprenticeship Support	Archaeological Market Survey 2017 March 2017				Archaeological Market Survey 2016 March 2016			
	have supported		would consider		have supported		would consider	
yes	2	11%	12	71%	1	4%	11	46%
no	17	89%	2	12%	23	96%	8	33%
don't know	0	0%	3	18%	0	0%	5	21%
total	19		17		4		24	

The Historic Environment Practice Trailblazer Apprenticeships programme launched in 2015¹⁴, with the Apprenticeships in historic environment practice being still under development in 2017¹⁵. This means that no specifically archaeological Apprenticeships had been delivered at the time of the survey; respondents may have been supporting generic Apprenticeships in admin, business finance *etc*, but not yet supporting formal Apprentices in Historic Environment Practice in the workplace – and an increasing proportion of respondents would consider doing so in the future.

¹⁴ Shepherd, N. 2016. Archaeological Apprenticeships.

<http://www.famearchaeology.co.uk/2016/03/archaeological-apprenticeships/>

¹⁵ Kate Geary pers. comm., 1st September 2017

7 PERCEPTIONS

Respondents were asked about their perceptions of particular issues.

On 31 March 2017, would you have agreed or disagreed with the following statements?

Individual responses will be aggregated in any survey report and your views will not be attributed to you without your permission

	strongly disagree	disagree	Unsure	agree	strongly agree
score	1	2	3	4	5
the economic climate for development will improve over the next 12 months	2	8	11	4	1
2017 average	2.77 (unsure) ↓ decrease on 2016				
2016 average	3.46 (unsure) ↓ decrease on 2015				
your heritage team will grow within the next 12 months	3	4	6	9	3
2017 average	3.20 (unsure) ↓ decrease on 2016				
2016 average	3.56 (agree) ↓ decrease on 2015				
your heritage team will contract within the next 12 months	3	15	5	3	1
2017 average	2.41 (disagree) ↑ increase on 2016				
2016 average	2.12 (disagree) ↑ increase on 2015				
late payment of bills is an increasingly significant problem for your business	0	8	2	12	4
2017 average	3.46 (unsure) ↑ increase on 2016				
2016 average	3.31 (unsure) ↓ decrease on 2015				
non-payment of invoices has been a significant problem for your business	2	13	2	5	3
2017 average	2.76 (unsure) ↑ increase on 2016				
2016 average	2.27 (disagree) ↓ decrease on 2015				
current national planning policy frameworks are making it easier to justify heritage work and revenue levels	1	6	5	12	1
2017 average	3.24 (unsure) ↑ increase on 2016				
2016 average	2.77 (unsure) ↓ decrease on 2015				
current national planning policy frameworks weaken the case for heritage work and revenue levels	2	11	6	3	2
2017 average	2.67 (unsure) ↓ decrease on 2016				
2016 average	2.93 (unsure) ↑ increase on 2015				
a shortage of heritage staff in LPAs is a major constraint on heritage projects	0	2	2	15	7

2017 average	4.04 (agree) ↓ decrease on 2016
2016 average	4.19 (agree) ↑ increase on 2015

In the table above, results have been aggregated, with each “strongly agree” response scoring five points, each “agree” scoring four, etc., and then an average of the responses calculated. Hence, for the average result to be 5.00, then every respondent would have strongly agreed with a statement, but if the average was 1.00 then every respondent would have strongly disagreed. The calculated average for 2017 is then categorised by which response that average is closest to, and compared with the 2016 scores.

Further comments on Perceptions:

Certain clients (e.g. minerals) operate very long payments terms (90 days from scanning of invoices). We've learnt to deal with it, but it does affect cash flow.

Implementation of NPPF still very inconsistent area to area

"National planning unsure as it isn't so much the legislation but how they are used + things have got a bit weaker

The current national planning policy frameworks are OK - it's what's proposed that will undermine our work e.g. the Planning and Infrastructure Bill. The effects of the Housing and Planning Act 2016 are not yet clear.

Respondents were unsure whether the economic climate for development would improve in the next 12 months, and their views had become less positive than they were in 2016, when in turn they were less confident than they had been in 2015. This should be considered alongside respondents' answers to the Business Confidence question on Market Conditions [5.2 above], where the overall view was also positive, but more cautious than a year before.

Typically, they were not sure that their heritage teams would grow in the next year, and were a little less confident of this than they had been in 2016. They were confident that their teams would not contract in size, but, again, views were slightly less positive than they had been in 2016.

Late payment of bills was a problem for an increasing number of respondents, as they felt more concerned about this than they had in 2016. Non-payment was becoming more of a concern, as respondents felt this was more of a problem than in 2016.

Respondents were unsure, but tended to agree with the statement that “current national planning policy frameworks are making it easier to justify heritage work and revenue levels”, and were also unsure, and tended to disagree with the assertion that “current national planning policy frameworks weaken the case for heritage work and revenue levels”. The responses to both of these questions were slightly more positive than they had been in 2016.

The sector continues to agree that a shortage of heritage staff in LPAs was a major constraint on heritage projects, although this was not felt as strongly as in 2016 (when it was felt more strongly than it had been in 2015, when in turn it was felt even more strongly than it had been in 2014). This clearly continues to be a serious issue for the respondents, and has to be seen in light of the ongoing loss of LPA archaeological advisory posts reported in Total Employment in UK Archaeology (2.1.5 above).

8 FURTHER COMMENTS

Division of income between waste and energy sectors is becoming blurred - we derive considerable income from biomass energy schemes, which use waste.

If HS2 and the rest of the long planned government infrastructure programme actually starts in 2017 - 18 then commercial practice will have capacity issues to address. If Brexit leads to the inability to recruit from Europe, the potential crisis will be exacerbated. HS2 and Historic England are failing to provide information and leadership to enable commercial practice to plan effectively for the future, and the potential career opportunities through apprenticeships have been compromised by the extreme slowness in setting up a standard, and so are too distant to help with the gathering capacity issue. In the meantime most commercial companies have reasonable order books due to growth in residential housing construction.

It is a good idea to separate our the market sectors a bit (I have added comments to the previous box which are relevant here). As no one comes out of university with vocational experience than the skills are the produce of the training and experience provided. I have never really understood the shortage of skills questions; we lose skills whenever anyone leaves but this is more a random thing depending on the individual who leaves. No one in the sector is very good at training so skills are always short when it comes to recruiting people and I would have to include our organisation here in relation to some of the staff who go elsewhere. As long as people are coming in at the graduate end then any skills shortage is of our own making; rather there is a lack of opportunity and support to provide robust training, especially in management, business and soft skills. There is of course a skills gap when it comes to finds and conservation as these are increasingly hard to procure from people getting close to retirement age. Only the bigger organisations can justify a full range of in house specialists

Our biggest issue is resourcing especially with experienced staff (esp. Project Officers and Managers). Field staff on recent large projects have come from all over Europe, particularly Spain and Italy. Our response has been to employ full time training officers as we try to fast-track employees and embed our recording systems.

Thanks for fixing the glitch

The division into categories of information you require is rather time-consuming and may put organisations off in filling in the survey. Could it be simplified?

there appears to be an error in 35 and 36. I wanted to say that we had both had NVQ posts in the past and would consider for the future, and to say that we would consider apprentices in the future, but an error message was returned. Also on 25 we do not breakdown between commercial and residential/industrial but I have provided figures for what we do have data for

While infrastructure may sustain archaeology over the coming few years, there is a significant risk that the market in other sectors will be damaged by uncertainties around Brexit and the continued imbalances in the UK economy. Planning de-regulation and local authority cuts risk undermining policy and regulatory support. There is a significant danger that while we face unprecedented demand, the foundations of commercial archaeology are being undermined. Next year looks rosy, and possibly the next few, but I am very concerned for the medium term.

APPENDIX – QUESTIONNAIRE

**Chartered
Institute for
Archaeologists**

FAME
Federation of Archaeological Managers & Employers

Archaeological Market Survey 2017

Dear Colleague,

FAME and CIFA, supported by Historic England, have appointed Landward Research Ltd to undertake annual surveys of suppliers to the **Archaeological Market**.

I would like to ask you if you could please give up some of your time to answer the questions below. We seek information as it applied to your organisation on 31 March 2017 – end of financial year 2016-17.

This survey will extend the information gathered by the previous **Archaeological Market Survey 2016** and earlier surveys in this series.

You can save the questionnaire at any stage and to return to it later (by following the link in your invitation email). You can also print the entire questionnaire from any screen using the buttons at top right of each page.

The deadline for responses is Friday 23 June 2017.

Your responses are fully confidential and will not be seen by any individual other than myself.

If you require further advice or information, please email hms@landward.eu.

Please complete the form by 23 June 2017.

Kenneth Aitchison Executive Director Landward Research Ltd

Landward Research Ltd is an Accredited Company Partner of the Market Research Society

1. Please enter your organisation's name (to avoid duplicate entries being made)

2. Please provide an email address where you can be contacted in the event of any queries

3. Is your organisation a member of FAME?
 - yes no
4. Is your organisation a CIFA Registered Organisation?
 - yes no
5. How is your organisation legally constituted?
please check multiple categories if appropriate
 - private limited company (ltd)
 - public limited company (plc)
 - registered charity
 - constituent part of a local planning authority
 - constituent part of a university
 - other

6. Where is the head office of your organisation located?

7. Are you also answering on behalf of any subsidiary offices? If so, please indicate where they are located?

East of England East Midlands Greater London North East England
 North West England South East England South West England West Midlands
 Yorkshire and the Humber Scotland Wales Northern Ireland
 outside the UK - in the EU outside the UK - not in the EU

8. In which year did your organisation begin trading (in applied archaeology)?

Chartered Institute for Archaeologists

Archaeological Market Survey 2017

Staff Numbers

9. How many full-time staff were based in your UK offices on 31 March 2017?

Please include all full-time or full-time equivalent staff, together with part-time staff, using estimates of full-time equivalency - for example, a member of staff working 2.5 days a week should be counted as 0.5.
 Fee-earners: members of staff whose time can be billed to clients.

	FTE
total UK staff (managerial, professional, technical and administrative) employed	
total UK-based fee earners working full-time	

10. Of your UK-based staff, how many were:

	FTE
British (UK subjects)	
nationals of other EU states	
nationals of other countries (non-UK, non-EU)	

11. How many full-time staff were permanently based outside the UK on 31 March 2017?

Please include all full-time or full-time equivalent staff, together with part-time staff, using estimates of full-time equivalency - for example, a member of staff working 2.5 days a week should be counted as 0.5.
 Fee-earners: members of staff whose time can be billed to clients.

	FTE
total non-UK based staff (managerial, professional, technical and administrative) employed	
total non-UK based fee earners working full-time	

12. How many UK members of staff (FTE) did your organisation have one year ago, on 31 March 2016 - the census date for the previous Archaeological Market Survey 2016?

13. How many of your members of staff were working on each of the following types of contract or agreement on 31 March 2017?

	full-time	part-time
permanent		
fixed term		
casual		
volunteer		

14. What level of staff turnover did you experience between 1 April 2016 and 31 March 2017?

15. If you had staff in the period between 1 April 2016 and 31 March 2017, do you believe that these people left the profession or stayed within it with different employers?
 for in March 2016) us in March 2016) us in March 2016) were not working for us in March 2016)

all left the profession
 most left the profession
 even split
 most found alternative employment
 all found alternative employment

16. Did salaries at your organisation typically rise or fall between March 2016 and March 2017? (NB - not total salary bill)
 when comparing changes to inflation, please consider the rate of inflation at the date of the salary settlement.

rose by above inflation
 rose by inflation
 unchanged
 fell by up to 10%
 fell by over 10%

17. How did your charge out rates change in the year to the end of March 2017, and by how much do you expect them to change in 2018-17?

by what percentage did your charge-out rates increase (+) or decrease (-) over the year ending 31 March 2017?

by what percentage do you anticipate that your rates will increase (+) or decrease (-) over the year ending 31 March 2018?

Chartered
Institute for
Archaeologists

Federation of Archaeological Managers & Employers

Archaeological Market Survey 2017

18. What was your annual turnover for work in the UK (in £) in financial year 2016-17?

Please enter full numbers of pounds, eg 725000, not decimal fractions of millions etc.

If your accounting period does not run from April to March, please indicate fee income for the nearest 12-month period for which audited figures are available, making clear which period they cover. Guidance on types of work to be included is in the Note to Respondents on the next page. If your fee income for the year exceeded £5 million, we will ask you to provide a breakdown of at least part of this fee income in the next page.

	£
your UK turnover in year ending 31 March 2017	

19. How was this income distributed between clients' or funders' locations in the UK?

please answer in terms of approximate percentages. Total must =100%.

20. What was your annual turnover from non-UK sources (in £) in financial year 2016-17?

Please enter full numbers of pounds, eg 725000, not decimal fractions of millions etc.

If your accounting period does not run from April to March, please indicate fee income for the nearest 12-month period for which audited figures are available, making clear which period they cover. Guidance on types of work to be included is in the Note to Respondents on the next page. If your fee income for the year exceeded £5 million, we will ask you to provide a breakdown of at least part of this fee income in the next page.

	£
your turnover from non-UK sources (including Republic of Ireland) in year ending 31 March 2017	

21. How do you anticipate overall turnover levels changing between last year - 2016-17 - and the next year, 2017-18?

please answer as a percentage figure, using a negative if you anticipate turnover falling

	%
predicted % change in turnover between years ending 31 March 2017 and 31 March 2018	

22. What was your annual profit (or surplus) (in £) in financial year 2016-17?

Please enter full numbers of pounds, eg 725000, not decimal fractions of millions etc.

If you made a loss in 2016-17, please enter a negative figure.

--	--

	£
your profit or surplus (plus or minus) in the year ending 31 March 2017	

23. What level of financial contributions did you make to community, public archaeology or education in financial year 2016-17?

Please enter full numbers of pounds, eg 1200000, not decimal fractions of millions etc

If your accounting period does not run from April to March, please indicate fee income for the nearest 12-month period for which audited figures are available, making clear which period they cover. Guidance on types of work to be included is in the Note to Respondents on the next page. If your fee income for the year exceeded £5 million, we will ask you to provide a breakdown of at least part of this fee income in the next page.

	£
your contribution to the community, public archaeology and education which has not been paid for directly by a client	

24. Please estimate your UK turnover from the following sources in the year ending 31 March 2017

Please enter full numbers of pounds, eg 1200000, not decimal fractions of millions etc

	£
private sector clients	
national agencies (Historic England, Historic Environment Scotland, Cadw etc)	
central government departments and agencies	
district, county or unitary councils (local planning authorities)	
other public bodies (including universities, public-private partnerships and local enterprise partnerships)	
community groups (including I&F projects, town and parish councils and neighbourhood forums)	

Chartered Institute for Archaeologists

Archaeological Market Survey 2017

25. Market Sectors

Please do not include non-UK turnover in this section

In the column headed "UK income", please indicate your UK income in the year ending 31 March 2017 for the work in each of the sectors listed.

Please enter full numbers of pounds, eg 1250000, not decimal fractions of millions etc.

To avoid double counting, please do not include fee income from any commission in more than one box. The total for this column must not exceed total fee income reported under turnover in the question above. If you are unsure about which sector to attribute a particular commission to, please refer to the Note to Respondents below.

In the two columns headed "2016-17" and "2017-18", please indicate whether your turnover in the UK market for each of the sectors listed grew, declined or was unchanged from the previous year in 2016-17 and whether you think it will grow, decline or be unchanged in 2017-18.

	UK income 2016-17	2016-17			2017-18		
	£	declined	unchanged	grew	will decline	will not change	will grow
Construction							
Residential development		<input type="radio"/>					
Commercial and industrial		<input type="radio"/>					
Retail and town centres		<input type="radio"/>					
Leisure, sport, entertainment and tourism		<input type="radio"/>					
Infrastructure							
Minerals		<input type="radio"/>					
Waste		<input type="radio"/>					
Transport		<input type="radio"/>					
Energy		<input type="radio"/>					
Telecommunications		<input type="radio"/>					
Water supply		<input type="radio"/>					
Education		<input type="radio"/>					
Health		<input type="radio"/>					
Research and public archaeology							
Community projects and HLF		<input type="radio"/>					
National agencies and university grants		<input type="radio"/>					
Local authority initiatives		<input type="radio"/>					
Other research and public archaeology		<input type="radio"/>					
Other services							
Heritage conservation		<input type="radio"/>					
Assistance to LPAs in delivering development control services		<input type="radio"/>					
Any other services not categorised above		<input type="radio"/>					

Notes to Respondents

Please do not include non-UK planning fee income in this section.

Inevitably there is some overlap between the categories identified in this section. To avoid double-counting, IT IS ESSENTIAL that income from any particular commission is entered in only one of the categories offered. The aggregate income shown in this table must should not exceed your figure for total UK planning fee income in Value of work undertaken and funding sources.

Work connected with specific development projects (including site-specific representations on LDFs) should be included in the relevant category under the headers "Construction" or "Infrastructure". Sector-specific planning work such as transport plans, housing land availability studies etc should also be included under these headings.

Work unconnected with specific development projects or types should be included at the relevant rows.

CIFA Chartered Institute for Archaeologists

FAIMIE
Federation of Archaeological Managers & Employers

Archaeological Market Survey 2017

26. Which forms of client contract do you routinely use?
check as many as apply

ICE (short form or alternatives) Other

NEC3 (various - family of contracts)

Bespoke

Client's standard T&Cs

Your own organisation's standard T&Cs

Exchanges of letters / emails

None

**Chartered
Institute for
Archaeologists**

F A I M E
Federation of Archaeological Managers & Employers

Archaeological Market Survey 2017

27. At the end of March 2017, did you anticipate any changes to your staffing levels over the next year (to 31 March 2018)?

Other comments?

28. On 31 March 2017, did you believe that market conditions would deteriorate over the next 12 months? (to 31 March 2018)

Other comments?

29. At the end of March 2017, did you expect any archaeological practices to cease trading over the next 12 months?

Other comments?

30. Did you have any plans to expand your business significantly over twelve months from March 2017 (e.g. in premises, vehicles, capital equipment)?

Other comments?

**Chartered
Institute for
Archaeologists**

Federation of Archaeological Managers & Employers

Archaeological Market Survey 2017

31. In the twelve months to the end of March 2017, did your organisation lose skills in any of these areas?

<input type="checkbox"/> fieldwork (intrusive or non-intrusive)	<input type="checkbox"/> providing advice to clients	<input type="checkbox"/> artefact or ecofact conservation
<input type="checkbox"/> post-fieldwork analysis	<input type="checkbox"/> desk-based or environmental assessment	<input type="checkbox"/> data management
<input type="checkbox"/> other		

32. In the twelve months to the end of March 2017, did your organisation have to buy-in skills in any of these areas?

<input type="checkbox"/> fieldwork (intrusive or non-intrusive)	<input type="checkbox"/> providing advice to clients	<input type="checkbox"/> artefact or ecofact conservation
<input type="checkbox"/> post-fieldwork analysis	<input type="checkbox"/> desk-based or environmental assessment	<input type="checkbox"/> data management
<input type="checkbox"/> other		

33. In the twelve months to the end of March 2017, did your organisation invest in skills training in any of these areas?

<input type="checkbox"/> fieldwork (intrusive or non-intrusive)	<input type="checkbox"/> providing advice to clients	<input type="checkbox"/> artefact or ecofact conservation
<input type="checkbox"/> post-fieldwork analysis	<input type="checkbox"/> desk-based or environmental assessment	<input type="checkbox"/> data management
<input type="checkbox"/> other		

34. On 31 March 2017, did you think there were skills shortages across the applied archaeological practice sector in any of these areas?

<input type="checkbox"/> fieldwork (intrusive or non-intrusive)	<input type="checkbox"/> providing advice to clients	<input type="checkbox"/> artefact or ecofact conservation
<input type="checkbox"/> post-fieldwork analysis	<input type="checkbox"/> desk-based or environmental assessment	<input type="checkbox"/> data management
<input type="checkbox"/> other		

35. On 31 March 2017, had you or were you considering supporting a member of staff to gain a vocational qualification in archaeological practice (NVQ)?

	yes	no	don't know
have supported a member of staff in the past	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
would consider supporting a member of staff in the future	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

36. On 31 March 2017, had you or were you considering supporting a member of staff to undertake an Apprenticeship in Historic Environment Practice?

	yes	no	don't know
have supported a member of staff in the past	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
would consider supporting a member of staff in the future	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

**Chartered
Institute for
Archaeologists**

FAMIE
Federation of Archaeological Managers & Employers

Archaeological Market Survey 2017

37. On 31 March 2017, would you have agreed or disagreed with the following statements?

Individual responses will be aggregated in any published survey report and your views will not be attributed to you without your permission

	strongly agree	agree	unsure	disagree	strongly disagree
non-payment of invoices has been a significant problem for your business	<input type="radio"/>				
current national planning policy frameworks weaken the case for heritage work and revenue levels	<input type="radio"/>				
the economic climate for development will improve over the next 12 months	<input type="radio"/>				
your heritage team will grow within the next 12 months	<input type="radio"/>				
your heritage team will contract within the next 12 months	<input type="radio"/>				
current national planning policy frameworks are making it easier to justify heritage work and revenue levels	<input type="radio"/>				
late payment of bills is an increasingly significant problem for your business	<input type="radio"/>				
a shortage of heritage staff in LPAs is a major constraint on heritage projects	<input type="radio"/>				

Any other comments?

CIFA Chartered Institute for Archaeologists

FAIMIE
Federation of Archaeological Managers & Employers

Archaeological Market Survey 2017

38. If you have any further comments on your responses, or on the state of commercial archaeology in general, please let us know. FAIMIE and CIFA would also particularly value respondents' views on the type of market information you would most value in future surveys.

Please complete your response by Friday 23 June 2017